

5 Years with Recurrent Diarrhoea: A Delayed Diagnosis of Crohn's Disease in a Kenyan Hospital

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Abstract: Crohn's disease (CD) and ulcerative colitis (UC) are the clinical variants of inflammatory bowel disease (IBD), which are autoimmune diseases characterised by chronic intestinal inflammation with both intestinal and extraintestinal manifestations. CD can affect the entire gastrointestinal tract, while UC affects only the colon and rectum, among other differences. IBD is considered an uncommon disease in sub-Saharan Africa due to a lack of awareness of the disease, deficiencies in clinical and diagnostic capacities, and a possibly high rate of misdiagnosis due to more common alternative infectious gastrointestinal diagnoses. In this study, we present the case of a 35-year-old Kenyan woman with a delayed diagnosis of CD who was managed with oral prednisone and sulfasalazine with a favourable response and has subsequently been in clinical remission on supervised follow-up. We call awareness to the existence of IBD, including CD, in the rural Kenyan communities and the role of diagnostic endoscopy in evaluating chronic or recurrent diarrhoea.

Keywords: Crohn's disease, inflammatory bowel disease, ulcerative colitis, Kenya.

1. INTRODUCTION

Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) is comprised of Crohn's disease (CD) and ulcerative colitis (UC). These are autoimmune diseases characterised by chronic intestinal inflammation due to disordered host-microbial interactions in genetically susceptible individuals (1, 2). Patients present with recurrent diarrhoea which can be watery or bloody; rectal bleeding; nausea and vomiting; cramping abdominal pain; fatigue; weight loss; and general debility. They might also experience other symptoms outside the intestines (extra-intestinal manifestations), such as skin issues (like erythema nodosum and pyoderma gangrenosum), joint problems (like sacroiliitis and ankylosing spondylitis), eye issues (like iritis and uveitis), and liver or bile duct problems (like primary sclerosing cholangitis), among others (1). UC uniformly affects the superficial mucosa of the colon and rectum only. On the other hand, CD can affect any portion of the luminal gastrointestinal tract from the mouth (aphthous ulcers) to the perianal region and often involves all layers of the bowel wall. About 80% of CD affects the ileum and colon (3). CD has a bimodal distribution between the ages 15 and 30 and 40 and 60 years (2). The typical clinical scenario for CD is a young patient presenting with recurrent cramping abdominal pain, chronic diarrhoea which may be bloody, weight loss, and fatigue (4). Several gastrointestinal society guidelines are available to guide the diagnosis, severity

classification, management, prognosis, and follow-up of patients with CD, including the American College of Gastroenterology (ACG) and the European Crohn’s and Colitis Organisation (ECCO) (5, 6). In summary, early diagnosis of CD should be based on the risk factor profile, clinical presentation, colonoscopy with biopsy findings (see Figure 1 below (7)), and adjunctive imaging of the small bowel, such as CT and MRI enterography. We should distinguish CD from UC as captured in Table 1 below. Based on the severity and complications of CD, management may be both medical and surgical. Some of the medications for CD include oral 5-aminosalicylates (like sulfasalazine and mesalamine), oral steroids (like prednisone and budesonide), immunomodulators (like azathioprine, 6-mercaptopurine, and methotrexate), and biologic agents (like infliximab and adalimumab).

Figure 1: Typical endoscopic features of Crohn’s disease. (A) Longitudinal ulcers, (B) cobblestone appearance, and (C) aphthous ulcers showing a longitudinal array (7).

Table 1: Differences between ulcerative colitis and Crohn’s disease (1, 2).

PARAMETER	ULCERATIVE COLITIS	CROHN’S DISEASE
Age of onset	15-30; 60-80	15-30, 40-60
Smoking	May prevent disease	May cause disease
Appendectomy	Protective	Not protective
Monozygotic twins	6% concordance	58% concordance
Upper gastrointestinal tract involvement	Never	Yes
Distal ileum	Never	Very common
Colon	Always	Common
Rectum	Never	Rarely
Histologic findings	Mucosa and submucosal inflammation, polymorphonuclear cell aggregates	Transmural inflammation, presence of granulomas
Endoscopic findings	Continuous lesions, presence of crypts, formation of residual mucosal tissue. No fistulae or strictures	Skip lesions, strictures, linear ulcerations, fistulae, cobblestone appearance

2. CASE SUMMARY

Clinical history and examination

A 35-year-old lady, single mother of 1, from Nakuru Town, Nakuru County, Kenya, first presented to us in October 2022 as a referral for colonoscopy with a long-standing history of recurrent oral ulcerations, cramping abdominal pains, postprandial vomiting, bloody diarrhoea, fatigue, and weight loss of about 10kg in the last 5 years. She also had associated “painful, red eyes with poor vision” during the diarrhoeal episodes but had no joint pains. She had an abdominal CT scan report showing an abnormal thickening of the terminal ileum and entire colon wall. She had been treated at the local health centres since sometime in 2017, with multiple episodes of watery, mucoid, and blood-stained stool needing at least 3 to 5 admissions annually until 2022. The local health centres treated her for "dysentery", "typhoid", "gastroenteritis", "amoebiasis", and "food poisoning" using various antibiotics and loperamide. She’s the second of four siblings who are alive and well. She has had a form of cerebral palsy since childhood associated with on-off hallucinations following

childhood febrile convulsions. These are well controlled with olanzapine, and she is still under the care of her parents. At 8 years of age, she was treated for pulmonary tuberculosis. Her paternal grandfather reportedly had a recurrent bloody diarrhoeal illness, to which he reportedly succumbed 10 years ago.

At her initial presentation to us, she was anaemic, hypotensive, and weighed 42 kg. Notably, she had various oral ulcerations at various stages of healing and activity, epigastric tenderness without peritonism, and a digital rectal examination revealed a tender rectum with fresh blood on the examining finger but no obvious tumour. An interval eye exam showed a mild anterior uveitis with normal visual acuity bilaterally.

Clinical evaluation and diagnosis

She had a haemoglobin of 10.4 g/dl with an MCV of 89 fl, normal white cell count and platelets, normal liver and renal panels, and an elevated ESR of 60 mm/hr; she was HIV-negative with normal blood sugars and a negative pregnancy test. Her stool was loose and bloody with numerous leucocytes and mucus but no ova or parasites. Following a successful resuscitation, we did an oesophago-gastro-duodenoscopy (OGD) which showed fundal gastritis, with the histology revealing chronic, non-atrophic superficial antral gastritis (H. pylori negative). See Figure 2 below. A colonoscopy showed pancolitis with marked mucosal thickening, edema, ulcerations with skip lesions. See Figure 3 below. The histology showed active chronic colitis with chronic inflammatory infiltrates, crypt abscesses, no ova or parasites, and no neoplasia. See Figure 4 below.

Figure 2: Oesophago-gastro-duodenoscopy (OGD) findings above show gastritis in the fundus of the stomach.

Figure 3: The results of the colonoscopy reveal interspersed colonic ulcers with normal mucosa, resulting in the typical skip lesions. This can be observed in panels A to C, where panel A provides a close-up of the ulcerated and normal mucosa. Additionally, panel D displays a nodular thickening of the mucosa, giving the appearance of cobblestones.

Figure 4: Histology report.

Management and follow-up

In view of her symptomatology, endoscopy findings and histology report, we made a diagnosis of inflammatory bowel syndrome, most likely Crohn's disease (CD). We put her on sulfasalazine 500 mg twice daily, oral prednisone 40 mg daily and tapered it over a 4-week period, omeprazole 20 mg twice daily, antacid syrup, loperamide, yoghurt for its probiotic properties, and other supportive therapy. By the end of the second week since starting the treatment, the gastrointestinal symptoms had resolved, while the other extraintestinal symptoms resolved by the end of the second month, by which time she had also gained 6 kg of body weight. It has now been three and a half years since the diagnosis of CD. She is on regular follow-up at the medical clinic under the supervision of the physician, where she's been in remission most times on sulfasalazine at 500mg daily, as determined by the Crohn's Disease Activity Index. She gets 2 or 3 flare-ups annually associated with acute infectious colitis (bacillary and amoebic dysentery) or when she defaults on her medications. A follow-up CT scan of the abdomen-pelvis was normal 2 years into her current treatment. She has had no clinical features to suggest any complications from the CD and no need for surgery. She weighed 65 kg in April 2025 and was asymptomatic. She currently enrolls in a beauty and cosmetics course at a tertiary institution in Nakuru Town and uses Norplant for contraception.

3. DISCUSSION

Our patient is a young woman whose symptoms began at about 30 years of age, comprising recurrent cramping abdominal pains, diarrhoea (at times bloody), weight loss, and fatigue. Her evaluation revealed mild anaemia, elevated ESR, and anterior uveitis. Endoscopy revealed fundal gastritis and a pancolitis sparing the rectum with associated skip lesions and a cobblestone appearance of the colonic mucosa. The histology showed a chronic active colitis with crypt abscesses, notwithstanding possible inadequacies with tissue sampling during the colonoscopy. These features are in keeping with CD (1). Her paternal grandfather had succumbed 10 years earlier to a bloody diarrhoeal illness, which could have been CD. CD has well-known genetic linkages, including the *NOD2* locus and more than 140 other loci (8). Notably, IBD is considered an uncommon disease in sub-Saharan Africa, possibly due to low exposures to environmental risk factors described in high-income countries, a possibly different genetic susceptibility, a lack of awareness of the disease, deficiencies in clinical and diagnostic capacities, and a possibly high rate of misdiagnosis due to more common alternative infectious differential diagnoses (9). There are no published epidemiological or clinical management data on IBD, much less CD, in Kenya. It is therefore of no surprise that since 2017, when her symptoms began, she had been variously treated for infectious causes in the peripheral health facilities and had not been seen by a physician for consideration of IBD until she was referred to us. There is an urgent need to create awareness of IBD among clinicians practising in the rural communities in Kenya with emphasis on colonoscopy with biopsy as a basic requirement for evaluating chronic or recurrent diarrhoea (5, 6). Based on

the ACG and ECCO guidelines, we rationalised her treatment medically, as she had no indications for surgery at the index review nor presently. She responded to oral prednisone and sulfasalazine as her main therapy and has been in clinical remission as determined by an online calculator of the Crohn's Disease Activity Index in each of her clinic visits (10). She has had a few flare-ups due to infections and defaulting on her medications. Prednisone and sulfasalazine are more available and affordable compared to mesalamine, oral budesonide, and the monoclonal antibodies (11).

4. CONCLUSION

The natural history and true burden of IBD (including CD) in sub-Saharan Africa in general, and Kenya in particular, remain largely unknown. Yet, as this case demonstrates, this disease is present in our rural communities in Kenya, creating the possibility of other undiagnosed or misdiagnosed cases. Deliberate efforts must be made to create awareness of the diagnosis and management of IBD in Kenya, with emphasis on the role of diagnostic colonoscopy in patients with recurrent or chronic diarrhoea and their prompt referral to physicians.

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Ethical Consideration

We obtained informed consent from the patient and her family for this case write-up.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Fakhoury M, Negrulj R, Mooranian A, Al-Salami H. Inflammatory bowel disease: clinical aspects and treatments. *J Inflamm Res.* 2014;7:113-20.
- [2] Ranasinghe IR, Tian C, Hsu R. Crohn Disease. *StatPearls.* Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing Copyright © 2025, StatPearls Publishing LLC.; 2025.
- [3] Tavakoli P, Vollmer-Conna U, Hadzi-Pavlovic D, Grimm MC. A Review of Inflammatory Bowel Disease: A Model of Microbial, Immune and Neuropsychological Integration. *Public Health Rev.* 2021;42:1603990.
- [4] Torres J, Mehandru S, Colombel JF, Peyrin-Biroulet L. Crohn's disease. *Lancet.* 2017;389(10080):1741-55.
- [5] Adamina M, Minozzi S, Warusavitarne J, Buskens CJ, Chaparro M, Verstockt B, et al. ECCO Guidelines on Therapeutics in Crohn's Disease: Surgical Treatment. *Journal of Crohn's and Colitis.* 2024;18(10):1556-82.
- [6] Lichtenstein GR, Loftus EV, Isaacs KL, Regueiro MD, Gerson LB, Sands BE. ACG Clinical Guideline: Management of Crohn's Disease in Adults. *Am J Gastroenterol.* 2018;113(4):481-517.
- [7] Lee JM, Lee KM. Endoscopic Diagnosis and Differentiation of Inflammatory Bowel Disease. *Clin Endosc.* 2016;49(4):370-5.
- [8] Liu JZ, Anderson CA. Genetic studies of Crohn's disease: past, present and future. *Best Pract Res Clin Gastroenterol.* 2014;28(3):373-86.
- [9] Watermeyer G, Katsidzira L, Setshedi M, Devani S, Mudombi W, Kassianides C. Inflammatory bowel disease in sub-Saharan Africa: epidemiology, risk factors, and challenges in diagnosis. *The Lancet Gastroenterology & Hepatology.* 2022;7(10):952-61.
- [10] Freeman HJ. Use of the Crohn's disease activity index in clinical trials of biological agents. *World J Gastroenterol.* 2008;14(26):4127-30.
- [11] Rajbhandari R, Blakemore S, Gupta N, Mannan S, Nikolli K, Yih A, et al. Crohn's Disease Among the Poorest Billion: Burden of Crohn's Disease in Low- and Lower-Middle-Income Countries. *Dig Dis Sci.* 2023;68(4):1226-36.